

Q7Z2Y5_NRK_numbeOfPeptides_11483

Q6A1A2_PDPK2_numbeOfPeptides_7738

P52564_MP2K6_numbeOfPeptides_6017

O75962_TRIO_numbeOfPeptides_12999

Q15772-1_SPEG_numbeOfPeptides_9089

Q8TDR2_STK35_numbeOfPeptides_8296

Q8IWB6_TEX14_numbeOfPeptides_330

Q9NVF9_EKI2_numbeOfPeptides_4

Q92519_TRIB2_numbeOfPeptides_6585

O60566_BUB1B_numbeOfPeptides_14117

P31152_MK04_numbeOfPeptides_18339

Q9H5K3_SG196_numbeOfPeptides_2599

Q96KG9_SCYL1_numbeOfPeptides_5164

Q8NER5_ACV1C_numbeOfPeptides_10431

P42338_PK3CB_numbeOfPeptides_3216

Q96RU7_TRIB3_numbeOfPeptides_3112

Q9BTU6_P4K2A_numbeOfPeptides_6116

Q6ZWH5_NEK10_numbeOfPeptides_6188

Q8NEB9_PK3C3_numbeOfPeptides_6516

P20594_ANPRB_numbeOfPeptides_6341

Q58A45_PAN3_numbeOfPeptides_2265

Q96DU7_IP3KC_numbeOfPeptides_3

P46734_MP2K3_numbeOfPeptides_6345

Q7Z695_ADCK2_numbeOfPeptides_4

Q9BRS2_RIOK1_numbeOfPeptides_13

Q504Y2_PKDCC_numbeOfPeptides_8325

O75747_P3C2G_numbeOfPeptides_2466

P48736_PK3CG_numbeOfPeptides_3136

Q16671_AMHR2_numbeOfPeptides_12606

P10398_ARAF_numbeOfPeptides_9632

Q5VST9-2_OBSCN_numbeOfPeptides_9752

Q9UQ88_CD11A_numbeOfPeptides_17430

Q9Y3S1_WNK2_numbeOfPeptides_10912

Q9Y6R4_M3K4_numbeOfPeptides_5166

Q86TB3_ALPK2_numbeOfPeptides_9047

O43283_M3K13_numbeOfPeptides_7389

Q9Y616_IRAK3_numbeOfPeptides_5375

Q5VST9-1_OBSCN_numbeOfPeptides_13123

P11801_KPSH1_numbeOfPeptides_11663

Q96L96_ALPK3_numbeOfPeptides_13115

P21127_CD11B_numbeOfPeptides_17410

Q8IVT5_KSR1_numbeOfPeptides_5636

Q9H792_PEAK1_numbeOfPeptides_5877

O14986_PI51B_numbeOfPeptides_1

O60307_MAST3_numbeOfPeptides_13854

P78356_PI42B_numbeOfPeptides_36

Q6VAB6_KSR2_numbeOfPeptides_4077

Q96Q40_CDK15_numbeOfPeptides_16021

O14733_MP2K7_numbeOfPeptides_6716

Q8TCG2_P4K2B_numbeOfPeptides_4969

Q38SD2_LRRK1_numbeOfPeptides_4737

Q8N165_PDK1L_numbeOfPeptides_9297

Q8IVW4_CDKL3_numbeOfPeptides_14151

Q92772_CDKL2_numbeOfPeptides_14922

P16066_ANPRA_numbeOfPeptides_11188

P30291_WEE1_numbeOfPeptides_9959

Q96C45_ULK4_numbeOfPeptides_8345

Q9UBF8_PI4KB_numbeOfPeptides_1372

Q15772-2_SPEG_numbeOfPeptides_12634

Q8TBX8_PI42C_numbeOfPeptides_2

Q99640_PMYT1_numbeOfPeptides_6323

Q96QS6_KPSH2_numbeOfPeptides_11320

O60229_KALRN_numbeOfPeptides_12080

Q9C098_DCLK3_numbeOfPeptides_11664

Q02846_GUC2D_numbeOfPeptides_4336

Q8NCB2_CAMKV_numbeOfPeptides_13413

P37023_ACVL1_numbeOfPeptides_12046

P42336_PK3CA_numbeOfPeptides_3563

Q7Z7A4_PXK_numbeOfPeptides_6988

A0A0B4J2F2_SIK1B_numbeOfPeptides_11424

Q05823_RN5A_numbeOfPeptides_12805

Q9NRP7_STK36_numbeOfPeptides_9585

Q8IV63_VRK3_numbeOfPeptides_3653

Q6ZS72_PEAK3_numbeOfPeptides_5308

Q96RU8_TRIB1_numbeOfPeptides_5835

Q6DT37_MRCKG_numbeOfPeptides_12878

Q8WZ42_TITIN_numbeOfPeptides_12211

Q13418_ILK_numbeOfPeptides_6625

Q5MAI5_CDKL4_numbeOfPeptides_15511

O00329_PK3CD_numbeOfPeptides_2929

P42356_PI4KA_numbeOfPeptides_2191

Q8IZL9_CDK20_numbeOfPeptides_15204

Q9Y4A5_TRRAP_numbeOfPeptides_14342

Q8TEA7_TBCK_numbeOfPeptides_1380

Q6P0Q8_MAST2_numbeOfPeptides_14186

O14730_RIOK3_numbeOfPeptides_226

Q8WU08_ST32A_numbeOfPeptides_7634

O00443_P3C2A_numbeOfPeptides_2691

Q9UHY1_NRBP_numbeOfPeptides_7244

Q7RTN6_STRAA_numbeOfPeptides_6763

Q9Y2H9_MAST1_numbeOfPeptides_14398

Q8NB16_MLKL_numbeOfPeptides_3810

Q96PN8_TSSK3_numbeOfPeptides_13094

P0C1S8_WEE2_numbeOfPeptides_6200

P53667_LIMK1_numbeOfPeptides_6288

Q6SA08_TSSK4_numbeOfPeptides_9851

O43930_PRKY_numbeOfPeptides_6398

Q8TAS1_UHMK1_numbeOfPeptides_17903

O60331_PI51C_numbeOfPeptides_19

Q8NE28_STKL1_numbeOfPeptides_3884

P53671_LIMK2_numbeOfPeptides_8342

Q16659_MK06_numbeOfPeptides_21422

Q96S38_KS6C1_numbeOfPeptides_5362

Q5T9C9_PI5L1_numbeOfPeptides_100

Q8NFD2_ANKK1_numbeOfPeptides_6278

O15021_MAST4_numbeOfPeptides_15308

O75063_XYLK_numbeOfPeptides_7171

Q15569_TESK1_numbeOfPeptides_8606

Q9HBY8_SGK2_numbeOfPeptides_13714

Q8IZE3_PACE1_numbeOfPeptides_4457

O14936_CSKP_numbeOfPeptides_10348

P45985_MP2K4_numbeOfPeptides_6504

P0C263_SBK2_numbeOfPeptides_7091

P51841_GUC2F_numbeOfPeptides_11710

Q6PHR2_ULK3_numbeOfPeptides_8595

Q96S53_TESK2_numbeOfPeptides_8286

Q9BXM7_PINK1_numbeOfPeptides_10882

P0C264_SBK3_numbeOfPeptides_7084

Q59H18_TNI3K_numbeOfPeptides_6209

Q8N2I9_STK40_numbeOfPeptides_5625

Q99570_PI3R4_numbeOfPeptides_8804

O76039_CDKL5_numbeOfPeptides_16096

Q9NSY0_NRBP2_numbeOfPeptides_1466

Q6P3W7_SCYL2_numbeOfPeptides_18023

Q96LW2_KS6R_numbeOfPeptides_9381

Q9Y6S9_RPKL1_numbeOfPeptides_3130

Q96MK3_FA20A_numbeOfPeptides_7117

Q99755_PI51A_numbeOfPeptides_70

Q9C0K7_STRAB_numbeOfPeptides_3373

Q86YV5_PRAG1_numbeOfPeptides_3461

P25092_GUC2C_numbeOfPeptides_1902

Q8NEV1_CSK23_numbeOfPeptides_9464

